

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me a great pleasure to announce the second regular issue of 2021. I want to thank all authors for contributing their sound research and the editorial board for the highly valuable reviews and comments for improvements. These contributions together with the generous support of the consortium members sustain the quality of our journal.

I would still like to expand our editorial board: If you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high quality proposals for special issues covering new topics and emerging trends. Please think of yourself and encourage your colleagues to submit high quality articles to our journal.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce three accepted papers from three different countries.

Alessia D'Andrea, Maria Chiara Caschera, Fernando Ferri, and Patrizia Grifoni from Italy introduce in their research MuBeFE, a Multimodal Behavioural Features Extraction Method based on Hidden Markov Models, which allows to extract information such as communicative intention, the social style and personality traits. Güldem Alev Özkök from Turkey aims in her research to model the process of data visualization (DV) and design to facilitate computational thinking (CT) of secondary-level students. Uyara Ferreira Silva and Deller James Ferreira from Brazil present a systematic literature review based on 400 articles of the literature on productive dialogues and emotional aspects in Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning (CSCL), and they also address emotional aspects used in debates with conflicting points of view in other contexts.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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